

This is the quantum gravitas model, and it goes as followed:

- This is a time twin paradox, and it is made of the following components: The prism paired with the crystal, the extra of the 4th wall, and the outcome of the magneto, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired prism with the crystal, then 4th wall, however, if 4th wall, then magneto, however, if magneto, then paired prism with the crystal. This twin paradox explained and shown before produces a conversion switch called the portals portal reference conversion projection switch, where the reference conversion twin paradox is made of the following components: The choomama paired with the humma, the extra of the hover, and the outcome of the cover, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired choomama with the humma, then hover, however, if hover, then cover, however, if cover, then paired choomama with the humma. This twin paradox explained and shown before proceeds to get switched by the projection switch twin paradox, which is made of the following components: The background paired with the middleground, the extra of the foreground, and the outcome of the alternative, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired background with the middleground, then foreground, however, if foreground, then alternative, however, if alternative, then paired background with the middleground. This twin paradox explained and shown before produces a name for the time twin paradox, which is the magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox. Then, there are 4 twin paradoxes that are created by the naming of the time twin paradox, where the 1st twin paradox is made of the following components: The prism paired with the choomama, the extra of the background, and the outcome of the magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired prism with the choomama, then background, however, if background, then magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, however, if magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, then paired prism with the choomama. The 2nd twin paradox is made of the following components: The crystal paired with the humma, the extra of the middleground, and the outcome of the magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired crystal with the humma, then middleground, however, if middleground, then magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, however, if magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas

quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, then paired crystal with the humma. The 3rd twin paradox is made of the following components: The 4th wall paired with the hover, the extra of the foreground, and the outcome of the magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired 4th wall with the hover, then foreground, however, if foreground, then magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, however, if magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, then paired 4th wall with the hover. The 4th twin paradox is made of the following components: The magneto paired with the cover, the extra of the alternative, and the outcome of the magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired magneto with the cover, then alternative, however, if alternative, then magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, however, if magically happen absolutely finally perpetually gravitas quantum gravitas perpetually finally absolutely happen magically time twin paradox, then paired magneto with the cover.

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